

What is your current education level?

Do you know what Citizen Science is?

Do you know what Open Science is?

How do you think Citizen Science could be connected to the Library and Information Science profession?

Have you ever noticed concepts and/or practices of Citizen Science being used as part of your curriculum?

Do you think that Citizen Science could become part of your curriculum as:

What would you consider the most appropriate curriculum level for the course to be part of?

Were a Citizen Science project to take place during one of your classes, would you be interested in participating?

What are the skills that you would expect to take from participating in a Citizen Science course?

